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İlkokul İngilizce Öğretmenlerinin İnternet Destekli Dil Eğitimine Dair Görüşleri

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Özet

İnternet destekli dil eğitimi (İDDE), çağdaş dil öğretimi stratejileri içerisinde sıkça kullanılan bir yöntemdir. Çalışmanın amacı, Türkiye'deki ilkokullarda çalışan İngilizce öğretmenlerinin İDDE'ye yönelik görüşlerini toplamaktır. Bu çalışma, sadece öğretmenlerin İnternet bazlı kaynakların kullanımı konusundaki görüşlerini değil, aynı zamanda internet kullanımı konusundaki becerilerini ve bu konuda özgüvenli hissedip hissetmediklerini de ölçmeyi amaçlamaktadır. Bununla birlikte, bu çalışma ile öğretmenlerin ne tür internet temelli aktiviteleri geniş ölçüde kullandıkları ve internet bazlı kaynakları sınıf içerisinde kullanırken hangi nedenlerin engel teşkil ettiği araştırılmaktadır. Bu nicel araştırma Türkiye'de ilkokullarda çalışan 20 ile 56 yaş aralığındaki 70 İngilizce öğretmenin fikirleri ile yürütülmektedir. Veriler Google Forms aracılığıyla 5 ölçekli anket ve çoktan seçmeli sorular ile toplanmaktadır. Sonuçlar öğretmenlerin İDDE'ye karşı pozitif bir tavır sergilediklerini ve bu konuda kendilerini büyük ölçüde geliştirmek istediklerini göstermiştir. Ancak bunun yanı sıra öğretmenlerin internet kullanımını ileride daha da geliştirmeleri için eğitime ihtiyaç duyup duymadıkları konusunda fikirlerinde bir tutarsızlık bulunmaktadır. Buna ilaveten, öğretmenlerin interneti kullanmakta kendilerini yeterli görmeleri ve İDDE konusunda duyarlı hissetmeleri hususunda düşünceleri değişkenlik göstermektedir. Sonuçlar İDDE'nin Türkiye'deki ilkokullarda nasıl işlediğini anlamak için belli bir noktaya kadar tartışılmıştır.

Anahtar Sözcükler: İnternet destekli dil eğitimi, ilkokullar, öğretmenlerin görüşleri, problemler.

Primary EFL Teachers' Views on Internet-Assisted Language Teaching

Abstract

Internet-assisted language education (IALE) is a frequently used method among contemporary language teaching strategies. The aim of the study is to collect the opinions of English teachers working in primary schools in Turkey regarding ILE. This study aims to measure not only the opinions of teachers on the use of Internet-based resources, but also their skills in using the Internet and whether they feel confident about it. In addition, this study investigates what kind of Internet-based activities teachers widely use and what reasons prevent them from using Internet-based resources in the classroom. This quantitative research is conducted with the opinions of 70 English teachers between the ages of 20 and 56 working in primary schools in Turkey. Data is collected through a 5-scale survey and multiple-choice questions via Google Forms. The results show that teachers have a positive attitude towards IALE and want to improve themselves in this regard to a great extent. However, there is an inconsistency in the opinions of teachers on whether they need training to further develop their Internet use

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in the future. In addition, teachers' opinions vary in terms of whether they consider themselves competent in using the Internet and whether they feel sensitive about IALE. The results are discussed to some extent in order to understand how the IALE operates in primary schools in Turkey.

Keywords: Internet-supported language education, primary schools, teachers' views, problems.

1. Introduction

In modern times technology has improved to such an extent that it affects almost every business segment in the world. It does not only make things easier but also plays an important role in making things work faster. Education is another field which is affected by the role of technology. Instead of utilizing technology merely for its own sake, educators and students should view it as a tool for students' intellectual progress and a medium of instruction (Nawaila, Kanbul, & Alhamroni, 2020). Nowadays the Internet enables people to reach any source of knowledge immediately, which provides both teachers and learners with fruitful ways. Teachers have been profoundly using the Internet both in and out of the classrooms to reach their aims about what they intend to give to their students. Also, students have been making use of Internet to improve their fund of knowledge in any subject they focus on. In the field of ELT (English Language Teaching), the Internet holds a wide range of materials which can be used for many purposes, such as teaching, using knowledge, application, practicing elements of reading, writing, listening and so on. However, in order to use such sources effectively, an EFL teacher must be aware of drawing advantage from them. At that point, he or she must act deliberately to make use of the Internet materials in the best way. Timing is a crucial aspect in teaching, so what sources are to be used should be planned beforehand so as not to cause any problems. He or she should also be aware of the students' attention and try to choose materials which must not cause them to be distracted, but rather play an efficient role in drawing their attention. Regarding these and many other variables, teachers' perspectives and understanding around this subject is quite important to infer about the use of Internet in EFL classrooms.

1.1 Statement of the Problem & Purpose

Today's educators should work in collaboration with peers and students to implement the student-centered learning vision (Jacobs & Toh-Heng, 2013). In Turkish primary EFL classrooms, teachers have been evolving language teaching from teacher-based classroom model to student-based one. According to this model, in primary schools, rather than teachers, students are taking an active role in EFL classes. Here, teachers play a role of a guide and try to show the ways to keep learners active and help them to participate as much as they can. So, rather than learning, the acquisition of language is the most important point to provide. In trying to reach such an aim, depending merely on course books is not enough to conduct a proper language teaching class. Along with it, cultivating task-based activities, role-playing models, reading, and listening comprehension tasks and activities help students to use the language in an authentic way. Consequently, there is a lot of flexibility of choice when using the internet, and learners are clearly motivated and excited about learning the language and acquiring knowledge (Pandit, 2011). In order to achieve this aim, benefiting from the Internet sources in the classroom could be a quite efficient way in helping students improve their acquisition toward the second language they are learning, however, at that point there are multiple variants which could either strengthen or weaken such a learning model. These can vary from limited time, schools' substructure to provide Internet, computer facilities or either teachers' or students' skills or interest in using Internet-based resources within classrooms. Therefore, the current study aims to clarify primary EFL teachers' thoughts on using Internet-assisted language teaching (IALT) in EFL classes located in Turkey.

1.2 Research Questions

Research Question 1: What are the general beliefs of EFL teachers toward IALT in classrooms?

Research Question 2: What type of Internet activities do EFL teachers prefer to use in classrooms?

Research Question 3: What are the reasons that prevent EFL teachers from using the Internet in classrooms?

2. Literature Review

The Internet has become to be used extensively at schools, but it is still discussed among educators whether it causes deficiency for learners along with its opportunities. Although at first sight one can guess that the Internet accelerates the learning process and provides varieties for learners, it might not work exactly as it seems in certain cases. Shin and Son (2007) states that for students who prefer a self-directed learning approach, the large amount

of knowledge connected via hypertext on the Web appears to be of great value. By means of such Internet sources, language teachers can personalize and individualize their sessions to foster student empowerment and autonomy (Warschauer, Turbee, & Roberts, 1996). Along with it, the Internet aids in implementing a personality-focused learning strategy, providing individualization and differentiation of instruction while taking into consideration students' abilities and inclinations (Tamara, 2020).

There are certain technological abilities and knowledge needed to use the Internet as a learning environment. This brings us to the question of how to fully utilize the vast amount of online materials, what technological abilities are required in particular, and how may learning assignments should be created so that students can use online resources? (Brandl, 2002). When the abilities are implemented correctly for both teachers and students then it is more possible to make use of Internet-based resources within classrooms. Tamara (2020) indicates that you can build up a set of test tasks on the computer as a foundation for tracking student achievement. The preparation of a lesson becomes a truly creative process, and the lesson is made intriguing and unforgettable by combining other methodological strategies with the computer's brightness, amusement, and originality. She also believes that students' cognitive processes can be substantially stimulated by using the Internet in the educational process, which also helps them develop their ability to work with a range of sources.

Agarwal (2010) thinks that due to the Internet's abundance of information sources, students no longer feel dependent on a single information source. There are several online resources available for each individual feature of any language. He also underlines that contemporary Internet resources offer wonderful opportunities with their creative challenges for both students and teachers. Due to lack of time and real materials, traditional classroom-based training does not give pupils a wide range of information, but Internet-based language learning (IBLL) can address all these issues. Nowadays multimedia usage is highly demanding in daily lives regardless of age, that is why it is motivating for students to use text, images, sounds, and animations in their projects and the Internet helps them develop their abilities in foreign language communication in the current technologically demanding environment. Along with the need to implement technology into EFL context and benefit from the internet, online multimedia technology is incorporated into the foreign language curriculum (Kanellopoulou & Giannakoulou, 2021).

2.1 Previous Studies

Internet-based sources have been highly used in EFL classes for many purposes. While they are aimed to make the class more enjoyable, in other ways they are also applied to make students learn faster or in a more precise way. In order to fulfill this purpose, teachers' thoughts, beliefs and experiences play a very important role in making use of IALT. This section aims to refer to related studies and make inferences from other teachers' beliefs to provide insight into the present study.

In their study, Shin and Son (2007) included 101 Korean secondary school EFL teachers' ideas and perceptions on the use of the Internet for language teaching purposes. According to the study's findings, there are three main factors that influence the use of the Internet in the classroom: teachers' personal interest in using the Internet, teachers' capacity to incorporate Internet resources into lesson plans, and teachers' access to computers and technical support in schools. According to the survey's findings, the majority of EFL instructors used the Internet for educational purposes. More than working directly with pupils in the classroom, teachers used the Internet to plan their lessons. According to the attendants who are Korean secondary school EFL teachers, the Internet activity that was most frequently used in their classes was web surfing. If they had Internet-assisted classes, the other 50 teachers who didn't utilize the Internet in the classroom, likewise wanted to use more than one Internet activity. They desired to engage their students in crosswords, games, and Web surfing activities in the classroom. Lastly, 50 non-users' top three reasons for not using the Internet in classrooms were ranked in the following order: limited computer facilities; limited time; teachers' limited computer skills (Shin & Son, 2007). These results light the way for the present study, yet it is important to underline that the above mentioned was conducted in 2007. So, it is crucial to see how teachers' perspectives and perceptions towards IALT has changed in 16 years with the development of technology and change of teachers' competence and approach toward using Internet-based resources in language education.

Verdugo and Belmonte (2007) investigated the effects of Internet-based instruction on six-year-old children's linguistic improvement in an English as a foreign language context. To gather quantitative and qualitative data about foreign language teachers' preconceptions, expectations, performance, and challenges while adopting computer-mediated instruction, a pre and post-questionnaire design was employed. According to the

results of the post-questionnaires, these teachers are aware that using computers in the classroom presents new challenges for educational strategies and classroom management. So, the teachers' enthusiasm gradually gave way to a more informed understanding of the benefits and drawbacks of an Internet-based curriculum. They still have a positive attitude toward the employment of ICTs in the classroom, nevertheless. (Verdugo & Belmonte, 2007).

3. Methodology

3.1 Participants and Context

70 EFL teachers who have experience with primary school students in Turkish primary schools attended the survey. 50 of the participants (71.4%) were female, and 20 of the participants (28.6%) were male. All these 70 teachers were given an online questionnaire via Google Forms, and they voluntarily participated in the survey by conveying their thoughts and decisions about IALT to primary students in Turkish primary schools. The age range of the participants was 20 – 56, yet the majority was between the age of 26 and 34 which consisted 52.9% of the participants. The second most populated age group was between the age of 20 and 25 (35.7%) which shows that the target group was mostly consisted of young teachers who are most likely to be competent with using Internet either in their daily lives or in the institutions they work.

3.2 Instrument

The research instrument was made up of 15 statements about IALT to get primary school teachers' thoughts on and two multiple-choice questions to get the ideas of the target group on the type of Internet activities used in the classroom and the reasons that prevent the teachers using the Internet in their classroom. The questionnaire was originally prepared and administered by Shin & Son (2007). The first part of the questionnaire included demographic questions about gender, age, teaching experience, the highest level of education, experience with primary levels, working full or part-time and working in a private or public institution. The second part consisted of 15 statements about IALT, and teachers' views were collected on a 5-point Likert Scale (1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree, 5 = strongly agree). On the third part a multiple-choice question was asked about the type of Internet activities that the participants use in their classrooms and 11 items were put as options for the teachers to select from. Lastly, on the fourth part another multiple-choice question was asked which was about the reasons that prevent the participants from using Internet activities in their classrooms. In that part, 8 items were presented to the teachers to select from.

3.3 Data Collection and Analysis

The researcher obtained permission from Dr. Jeong-Bae Son (Shin & Son, 2007) to be able to use the same questionnaire in the present research. A Google Forms link was shared with the 70 EFL teachers who participated in the study voluntarily. Over the course of 50 days all the participants filled in the questionnaire according to their ideas and experiences with primary levels. The results were collected by Google Forms and a quantitative analysis was conducted in the form of both percentage and frequency values.

4. Results

50 female and 20 male EFL teachers who have experience with primary levels in Turkish institutions attended the survey. The results of the questionnaire indicate that majority of the teachers tend to use Internet for educational purposes. Along with it, teachers prefer to use more than one type of Internet activities in the classroom to assist their language teaching processes. As shown in Figure 1, 65 out of 70 teachers (92.9%) use games as the mostly used Internet activity in classes. Then comes quizzes with 84.3% rate and video activities with the rate of 81.4%. However, the least used Internet activity in classrooms is e-mailing (12.9%) which is likely to show that EFL primary teachers in Turkey do not prefer using e-mails as a foreign language teaching tool. Next comes encyclopedias (14.3%) which could be found unnecessary for primary levels and text chatting (17.1%).

Figure 1. Types of Internet activities used in the classroom (N=70)

As shown in Figure 1, more than half of the attendants also prefer to use puzzles (61.4%) and crosswords (55.7%) in EFL classes which draw primary level groups' attention. Aside from them, even if they are below the average, the teachers still prefer to use web surfing (45.7) and on-line dictionaries (38.6%) remarkably within classrooms.

Figure 2. Reasons for preventing Internet use in the classroom (N=70)

According to the results shown in Figure 2, the most common reason that prevents EFL teachers from using the Internet is limited time (70%). So, teachers who have experience with primary levels in Turkey generally believe that using Internet activities in classroom is time consuming. In addition, half of the attendants (50%) believe that limited computer facilities hinder Internet-based teaching in EFL classes which shows that schools in Turkey do not provide a consistent database for Internet use. 20 of the teachers (28.6%) indicate that students' limited English ability prevents Internet use in the class, which is understandable for primary levels, so Internet-based resources that are appropriate to their levels should be selected. Moreover, 17 teachers (24.3%) see students' limited computer skills as a hindrance to apply Internet use in the classroom. However, so few attendants believe that they have limited computer skills (5.7%) or interest (2.9%). They do not also think students have limited interest (4.3%) in using Internet activities. Thus, it can be inferred that students in Turkish primary schools show interest towards Internet activities.

Figure 3. Teachers' responses to questionnaire items (N=70)

Teachers' perceptions and thoughts toward IALT are collected in 15 general questions. According to the quantitative study that includes 70 primary EFL teachers' views, Figure 3 indicates that majority of attendants believe that the Internet enables nonnatives speakers to be active in a rich learning environment. 61.4% of the participants strongly support using Internet tools in language teaching which becomes compulsory with modern language teaching strategies. Most EFL teachers also don't struggle with finding EFL/ESL materials on the WEB to apply within classroom. Because there are lots of paid or free websites in the WEB which enable teachers with loads of language teaching materials for many purposes. However, majority of the teachers (41.4%) are still unsure about replacing Internet resources with textbooks. This situation shows us that even if teachers are satisfied with Internet-based resources, they are still uncertain to use them as the main material. In this case it can be inferred that EFL teachers still have positive views towards tangible materials which enable students to touch, draw, erase or write on a paper in contemporary learning environment.

Figure 4. Teachers' responses to questionnaire items (N=70)

Figure 4 shows that half of the EFL teachers (50%) potentially believe that EFL/ESL websites are useful for teaching English. A great majority of the attendants (29.9%) basically support these websites' effectiveness. On the other hand, half of the EFL teachers (50%) clearly support the idea that the Internet is a good motivator for students in the classroom and the rest of the majority (32.8%) agrees to the motivational effect of the Internet. 39 out of 70 participants (55.7%) totally support that the use of Internet helps students improve their English skills. Likewise, 32 out of 70 attendants (45.7%) strongly agree to the belief that students can adapt to Internet resources themselves, since nowadays students grow up with using technology and the Internet abundantly. However, still 9 participants (12.8%) are unsure whether students can use the Internet resources for learning English themselves or not. Along with it, 5 teachers (7.1%) don't think and another 5 (7.17%) strongly refuse the idea that students can use Internet resources for learning English themselves.

Figure 5. Teachers' responses to questionnaire items (N=70)

As Figure 5 displays, majority of the EFL teachers support the idea of improving English by communicating with native speakers through chatting or e-mailing on the Internet (79.9%). As a significant step to acquire a language, one must use the language in his or her own way. Thus, using a language online provides an authentic input for the learners. Students might not always feel free to use the language they learn in a classroom atmosphere, but the Internet can break such boundaries. On the other hand, most of the teachers (72.7%) support the idea that IALT puts the learners in a much more attentive position, yet there is still a segment (15.7%) who can't decide whether the Internet draws as attention as it is expected.

11th and 12th items refer mainly to teachers rather than students and it can be inferred that even if 30 out of 70 (42.8%) attendants agree to take the responsibility of the success with the use of IALT, fewer EFL teachers (25.7%) strongly agree to take the responsibility. Along with them, 17.1% of the attendants can't decide if they are responsible for that. So, teachers may find using IALT quite beneficial, but they can't fully accept the responsibility of it which might still end up with teachers' seeing internet as an assistant tool, rather than the main instrument to implement language teaching. In relation to it, teachers still don't completely feel competent with using Internet-based resources within classroom which can cause them not to think having complete responsibility. While 22 out of 70 (31.4%) strongly acknowledge to be competent with using the Internet materials, 34 teachers (48.5%) merely agree to be competent with it.

Figure 6. Teachers' responses to questionnaire items (N=70)

According to Figure 6, most of the EFL teachers who attended the survey (78.5%) feel comfortable with integrating Internet materials into classroom curriculum, yet 41.4% of those agree with it while 37.1% strongly agree. So, there is still an uncertainty for teachers to use Internet-based resources coherently with the curriculum. In the 15th item teachers' strong desire to use Internet-based activities in classroom can be seen. However, 14th item gives us highly close outcome. Although 19 out of 70 participants (27.1%) lean towards improving their Internet literacy skills, 22.8% of participants disagree with it and 21.4% of the teachers do not ever think of getting training to improve themselves in that way. So, even if it may show primary EFL teachers' self-confidence toward using Internet-based resources clearly, it can never be denied that the Internet is a tool that updates itself day by day which requires improvement to keep up with regularly. As a result, 14th item leaves a question mark about whether primary EFL teachers in Turkey are competent about using the Internet and whether they are using IALT influentially.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

The overall data analysis shows that the participating teachers have faith in the potential of language technology through the use of Internet for teaching second languages in terms of their functional and communicative potential, which is in line with the results of the study conducted by Verdugo and Belmonte (2007). As in their study, the majority of the participants in our study also believe that the Internet plays a significant role in providing linguistic input by means of the materials that it provides in vocabulary, listening, reading etc.

Primary EFL teachers of the current study indicated that they know how to integrate Internet-based resources into classroom curriculum, yet most of them are not fully confident about it, which can be prevented by providing learners with some background about Internet-based activities and their link to their context. This kind of an approach can lead to a much more positive result in linking Internet-based activities with the curriculum. According to the results of the study the Internet is clearly an effective tool for teachers to benefit during the language teaching process and it holds a great number of materials that support language input given to students. However, adapting students merely to the Internet-based language teaching process does not seem to be possible yet. By taking the inadequacies of both teachers and students about implementing IALT permanently into ELT classrooms into account, it requires managing the traditional class after IALT sessions. Thus, rather than focusing merely on IALT, benefiting from it in a blended learning atmosphere is much more useful in an ELT atmosphere (Shin & Son, 2007). Even though there is a 16-years-period between these two studies and the Internet gradually improves itself with the abundance of sources in many fields including language teaching, the teachers who participated in the study are not still sure about to replace textbooks with Internet materials. So, it

shows that textbooks and traditional approaches in a way still help learners improve themselves. Although one click makes most of the things easier, paper and pencil still play an important role in providing language input for learners.

EFL/ESL websites are undoubtedly beneficial for students' language improvement according to the results of the questionnaire. Because they hold loads of distinctive materials that draw mainly the primary level students' attention. When providing students merely with the inputs of textbooks becomes dull, these websites play a role of a savior in changing the atmosphere and filling the class with positive energy. Just as Shin & Son (2007)'s study indicates, teachers are quite willing to use IALT in their classrooms to motivate their students along with helping them to improve their English as it can be seen in the results of the questionnaire. Nonetheless, when students want to practice Internet tools for language learning purposes themselves a problem might occur. Since the Internet is a vast universe, it is quite possible, especially for students of primary levels, to get lost in it. At that point, teachers should motivate their students to cooperate and collaborate in IALT, then teach them how to use the Internet sources in the most effective way (Shin & Son, 2007). So, in this contemporary language teaching model, the teacher plays a role of a guide to make the students active.

It is clearly seen from the study that EFL teachers believe that students can improve their communication skills by right ways of interaction either through e-mailing or chatting. Although it is easier to use these tools with the older young learners, it can still be initiated with the primary levels who have no difficulty with writing or reading. When teachers are able to carry out the process properly without forcing the students, it is possible to raise autonomous students who can use the language without having fear of failure. Plus, attention grabbing aspect of IALT is an efficient model to be benefited from within the classroom, which is strongly defended by 39.9% of the participants and agreed by 32.8%. In drawing primary EFL students' attention, games (92.9%), quizzes (84.3%) and video activities (81.4%) are used in the highest rate which are boosters to raise up students' energy and activate their language skills by promoting competitiveness.

While applying IALT model in EFL classrooms, teachers feel uncomfortable due to time limitation which is a preventive case. Because reaching to the desired material can sometimes take time because of some unfortunate situations like inefficacy in computer facilities of Turkish schools as it is also the same obstacle underlined in Shin and Son (2007)'s study. This study shows us that there is still insufficiency in Turkish institutions to conduct IALT properly. Regarding this, it can be thought that schools are to be assisted with adequate computer facilities, smart screens, and Internet basis to close the deficit.

Regarding all the benefits that the Internet provides for language teaching in EFL classrooms, teachers have quite positive views to apply IALT as much as they can in their classrooms but there is still vagueness about whether teachers are competent enough to use IALT effectively in classrooms according to the study. Because, although they mostly agree to be responsive and competent with using Internet resources in classrooms, less teachers are exactly confident about it. Moreover, while a high number of participants (41.4%) agree to know how to integrate IALT into existing curriculum, less (37.1%) is strongly confident with it. Along with these, the participants of our study do not react consistently to improve themselves by getting training in Internet literacy, skills which can actually be quite beneficial to use Internet-based resources in the best way. While 27.1% agree to it, 22.8% disagree and 21.4% reject such a training. Only 6 out of 70 (8.5%) strongly believe to get training for the improvement. As a result, it can be thought that the Internet is renewing itself day by day and the sources it brings are updated every day. Although teachers feel confident to use them in their language classes, professional trainings should be carried out periodically in institutions for teachers to help them guide their students in the Internet environment in the best way. All in all, the future lies in using technology efficiently in almost all fields.

6. Suggestions For Further Research

The current study mainly aimed to perceive primary EFL teachers' general views and perceptions toward IALT. However, the Internet is renewing itself day by day, thus the approach towards using it never stays the same. IALT techniques, approaches and methods are changeable which can vary from region to region, from one age group to the other or its effectiveness can differ from private institutions to public institutions depending upon their infrastructure, Internet access or technological capacities. By mainly taking these variables into consideration, future research can be conducted to focus on certain aspects in using IALT.

Researchers' Contribution Rate

The contribution rate of the authors is equal.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest in this research

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GENİŞLETİLMİŞ ÖZET

İnternet destekli dil eğitimi (İDDE), çağdaş dil öğretimi stratejileri içerisinde sıkça kullanılan bir yöntemdir. Çalışmanın amacı, Türkiye'deki ilkokullarda çalışan İngilizce öğretmenlerinin İDDE'ye yönelik görüşlerini toplamaktır. Bu çalışma, sadece öğretmenlerin İnternet bazlı kaynakların kullanımı konusundaki görüşlerini değil, aynı zamanda internet kullanımı konusundaki becerilerini ve bu konuda özgüvenli hissedip hissetmediklerini de ölçmeyi amaçlamaktadır.

Ankete, Türk kurumlarında ilköğretim düzeyinde deneyimi olan 50 kadın ve 20 erkek EFL öğretmeni katıldı. Anketin sonuçları, öğretmenlerin çoğunluğunun eğitim amaçlı İnternet kullanma eğiliminde olduğunu göstermektedir. Bununla birlikte, öğretmenler dil öğretim süreçlerine yardımcı olması için sınıfta birden fazla türde İnternet etkinliği kullanmayı tercih etmektedir. 70 öğretmenden 65'i (%92,9) sınıflarda en çok kullanılan İnternet etkinliği olarak oyunları kullanmaktadır. Ardından %84,3'lük oranla sınavlar ve %81,4'lük oranla video etkinlikleri gelmektedir. Ancak, sınıflarda en az kullanılan İnternet etkinliği e-posta (%12,9) olup, bu da Türkiye'deki EFL ilköğretim öğretmenlerinin yabancı dil öğretim aracı olarak e-posta kullanmayı tercih etmediklerini göstermektedir. Ardından, ilköğretim düzeyleri için gereksiz bulunabilecek ansiklopediler (%14,3) ve metin sohbeti (%17,1) gelmektedir.

EFL öğretmenlerinin İnternet kullanmasını engelleyen en yaygın neden sınırlı zamandır (%70). Yani,

Türkiye'de ilköğretim düzeyinde deneyimi olan öğretmenler genellikle sınıfta İnternet etkinliklerini kullanmanın zaman alıcı olduğuna inanmaktadır. Ayrıca, katılımcıların yarısı (%50), sınırlı bilgisayar olanaklarının EFL sınıflarında İnternet tabanlı öğretimi engellediğine inanmaktadır; bu, Türkiye'deki okulların İnternet kullanımı için tutarlı bir veri tabanı sağlamadığını göstermektedir. Öğretmenlerin 20'si (%28,6), öğrencilerin sınırlı İngilizce becerilerinin sınıfta İnternet kullanımını engellediğini belirtmektedir; bu, ilköğretim düzeyleri için anlaşılabilir bir durumdur; bu nedenle, kendi seviyelerine uygun İnternet tabanlı kaynaklar seçilmelidir. Dahası, 17 öğretmen (%24,3), öğrencilerin sınırlı bilgisayar becerilerinin sınıfta İnternet kullanımını uygulama konusunda bir engel olduğunu düşünmektedir. Ancak, çok az katılımcı, sınırlı bilgisayar becerilerine (5,7%) veya ilgiye (2,9%) sahip olduklarına inanmaktadır. Ayrıca, öğrencilerin İnternet etkinliklerini kullanma konusunda sınırlı ilgiye (4,3%) sahip olduklarını düşünmemektedirler. Bu nedenle, Türk ilköğretim okullarındaki öğrencilerin İnternet etkinliklerine ilgi gösterdiği sonucuna varılabilir.

Öğretmenlerin IALT'ye yönelik algıları ve düşünceleri 15 genel soruda toplanmıştır. 70 ilköğretim EFL öğretmenin görüşlerini içeren nicel çalışmaya göre, katılımcıların çoğunluğunun İnternet'in ana dili olmayan konuşmacıların zengin bir öğrenme ortamında aktif olmasını sağladığına inandığını göstermektedir. Katılımcıların %61,4'ü modern dil öğretim stratejileriyle zorunlu hale gelen dil öğretiminde İnternet araçlarının kullanılmasını güçlü bir şekilde desteklemektedir. Çoğu EFL öğretmeni ayrıca sınıfta uygulamak için WEB'de EFL/ESL materyalleri bulmakta zorluk çekmemektedir. Çünkü WEB'de öğretmenlere birçok amaç için çok sayıda dil öğretim materyali sağlayan çok sayıda ücretli veya ücretsiz web sitesi bulunmaktadır. Ancak öğretmenlerin çoğunluğu (%41,4) hala İnternet kaynaklarını ders kitaplarıyla değiştirme konusunda emin değildir. Bu durum bize, öğretmenler İnternet tabanlı kaynaklardan memnun olsalar bile, bunları ana materyal olarak kullanmaktan hala emin olmadıklarını göstermektedir. Bu durumda, EFL öğretmenlerinin öğrencilerin çağdaş öğrenme ortamında bir kağıda dokunmasını, çizmesini, silmesini veya yazmasını sağlayan somut materyallere karşı hala olumlu görüşlere sahip olduğu sonucuna varılabilir. EFL öğretmenlerinin yarısının (%50) EFL/ESL web sitelerinin İngilizce öğretmek için yararlı olduğuna güçlü bir şekilde inandığını göstermektedir. Katılımcıların büyük çoğunluğu (%29,9) temelde bu web sitelerinin etkinliğini desteklemektedir. Öte yandan, EFL öğretmenlerinin yarısı (%50) İnternet'in sınıftaki öğrenciler için iyi bir motivasyon kaynağı olduğu fikrini açıkça desteklerken, çoğunluğun geri kalanı (%32,8) İnternet'in motivasyonel etkisine katılmaktadır. 70 katılımcıdan 39'u (%55,7), İnternet kullanımının öğrencilerin İngilizce becerilerini geliştirmelerine yardımcı olduğunu tamamen desteklemektedir. Aynı şekilde, 70 katılımcıdan 32'si (%45,7), günümüzde öğrencilerin teknoloji ve İnternet'i bolca kullanarak büyüdükleri için, öğrencilerin İnternet kaynaklarına kendilerinin uyum sağlayabileceğine inanmaktadır. Ancak yine de 9 katılımcı (%12,8), öğrencilerin İngilizce öğrenmek için İnternet kaynaklarını kendilerinin kullanıp kullanamayacaklarından emin değildir. Bununla birlikte, 5 öğretmen (%7,1) düşünmediğini belirtirken, diğer 5 öğretmen (%7,17) ise öğrencilerin İngilizceyi kendi başlarına öğrenmek için İnternet kaynaklarını kullanabileceği fikrine şiddetle karşı çıkmaktadır.

EFL öğretmenlerinin çoğunluğu, İnternet üzerinden sohbet veya e-posta yoluyla ana dili İngilizce olan kişilerle iletişim kurarak İngilizceyi geliştirme fikrini destekliyor (%79,9). Bir dili edinmenin önemli bir adımı olarak, kişi dili kendi tarzında kullanılmalıdır. Bu nedenle, bir dili çevrimiçi kullanmak, öğrenenler için gerçek bir girdi sağlar. Öğrenciler, bir sınıf ortamında öğrendikleri dili kullanmakta her zaman özgür hissetmeyebilirler, ancak İnternet bu tür sınırları ortadan kaldırabilir. Öte yandan, öğretmenlerin çoğu (%72,7), IALT'nin öğrencileri çok daha dikkatli bir konuma getirdiği fikrini destekliyor, ancak İnternet'in beklendiği kadar dikkat çekip çekmediğine karar veremeyen bir kesim (%15,7) hala bulunmaktadır.

11. ve 12. maddeler öğrencilerden ziyade öğretmenlere atıfta bulunuyor ve 70 katılımcıdan 30'unun (%42,8) IALT kullanımıyla elde edilecek başarının sorumluluğunu almayı kabul etse bile, daha az EFL öğretmenin (%25,7) sorumluluğu almayı kesinlikle kabul ettiği sonucuna varılabilir. Bunlarla birlikte, katılımcıların %17,1'i bundan sorumlu olup olmadıklarına karar veremiyor. Bu nedenle, öğretmenler IALT'yi kullanmayı oldukça yararlı bulabilirler, ancak bunun sorumluluğunu tam olarak kabul edemezler ve bu da öğretmenlerin interneti dil öğretimini uygulamak için ana araç yerine yardımcı bir araç olarak görmelerine neden olabilir. Bununla ilgili olarak, öğretmenler hala sınıf içinde İnternet tabanlı kaynakları kullanma konusunda kendilerini tamamen yeterli hissetmiyorlar ve bu da onların tam sorumluluğa sahip olduklarını düşünmemelerine neden olabilir. 70 kişiden 22'si (%31,4) İnternet materyallerini kullanma konusunda güçlü bir şekilde yeterli olduklarını kabul ederken, 34 öğretmen (%48,5) yalnızca yeterli olduklarını kabul etmektedir.

Ankete katılan EFL öğretmenlerinin çoğu (%78,5) İnternet materyallerini sınıf müfredatına entegre etme konusunda rahat hissediyor, ancak bunların %41,4'ü buna katılırken %37,1'i buna kesinlikle katılıyor. Bu nedenle,

öğretmenlerin İnternet tabanlı kaynakları müfredatla tutarlı bir şekilde kullanmaları konusunda hala bir belirsizlik var. 15. maddede öğretmenlerin sınıflarda İnternet tabanlı etkinlikler kullanma konusunda güçlü bir istekleri olduğu görülebilir. Ancak 14. madde bize oldukça yakın bir sonuç veriyor. 70 katılımcıdan 19'u (%27,1) İnternet okuryazarlığı becerilerini geliştirmeye yönelmesine rağmen, katılımcıların %22,8'i buna katılmıyor ve öğretmenlerin %21,4'ü bu şekilde kendilerini geliştirmek için eğitim almayı hiç düşünmüyor. Bu nedenle, ilkököl EFL öğretmenlerinin İnternet tabanlı kaynakları kullanma konusunda özgüvenlerini açıkça gösterse bile, İnternet'in düzenli olarak güncellenmesi için iyileştirme gerektiren, kendini her geçen gün güncelleyen bir araç olduğu asla inkar edilemez. Sonuç olarak, 14. madde Türkiye'deki ilkököl EFL öğretmenlerinin İnternet kullanımı konusunda yeterli olup olmadıkları ve IALT'yi etkili bir şekilde kullanıp kullanmadıkları konusunda soru işareti bırakmaktadır.

Genel veri analizi, katılımcı öğretmenlerin işlevsel ve iletişimsel potansiyelleri açısından ikinci dilleri öğretmek için İnternet kullanımı yoluyla dil teknolojisinin potansiyeline inandıklarını göstermektedir; bu, Verdugo ve Belmonte (2007) tarafından yürütülen çalışmanın sonuçlarıyla uyumludur. Çalışmalarında olduğu gibi, çalışmamızdaki katılımcıların çoğunluğu da İnternet'in kelime bilgisi, dinleme, okuma vb. konularda sağladığı materyaller aracılığıyla dilsel girdi sağlamada önemli bir rol oynadığına inanmaktadır.

Mevcut çalışmadaki ilköğretim EFL öğretmenleri, İnternet tabanlı kaynakları sınıf müfredatına nasıl entegre edeceklerini bildiklerini ancak çoğunun bu konuda tam olarak emin olmadıklarını belirtmişlerdir; bu, öğrencilere İnternet tabanlı etkinlikler ve bunların bağlamlarıyla bağlantıları hakkında biraz arka plan sağlanarak önlenabilir. Bu tür bir yaklaşım, İnternet tabanlı etkinlikleri müfredatla ilişkilendirmede çok daha olumlu bir sonuca yol açabilir. Çalışmanın sonuçlarına göre İnternet, öğretmenlerin dil öğretimi sürecinde faydalanabilecekleri etkili bir araçtır ve öğrencilere verilen dil girdisini destekleyen çok sayıda materyal içerir. Ancak, öğrencileri yalnızca İnternet tabanlı dil öğretim sürecine adapte etmek henüz mümkün görünmüyor. Hem öğretmenlerin hem de öğrencilerin IALT'yi ELT sınıflarına kalıcı olarak uygulama konusundaki yetersizlikleri hesaba katıldığında, IALT oturumlarından sonra geleneksel sınıfın yönetilmesi gerekiyor. Bu nedenle, yalnızca IALT'ye odaklanmak yerine, karma bir öğrenme ortamında bundan yararlanmak, bir ELT ortamında çok daha faydalıdır (Shin & Son, 2007).